

Properties of cryogenic Epoxy Resin Matrix Composites prepared by RTM Process

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ABSTRACT

A resin transfer molding (RTM) epoxy resin R608 for cryogenic application was developed, and their RTM processability and the mechanical properties at 80°C, RT and -196°C were examined. M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites were prepared via a RTM process, and their mechanical properties at 80°C, RT and -196°C were examined. The effects of cryogenic temperature and (-196°C—80°C) cryogenic-cycles on the mechanical properties were studied. According to the results, the RTM process time window of R608 was more than 9 hour, and the breaking elongation of R608 was 6.1% at room temperature and 2.3% at -196°C, respectively. Besides, the T_g of composites was 117°C and the effect of cryogenic temperature on tensile strength of the composites was small; while as the decrease of temperature, the flexural strength, compression strength, interlaminar shear strength and impact strength were improved remarkably. The composite can resist 300 cryogenic-cycles; after a 300 cryogenic-cycles, their mechanical strength and fracture toughness have not declined obviously.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the rapid development of spacecraft, superconducting cable, and large cryogenic engineering projects, the application of fiber reinforced epoxy resin matrix composite materials under cryogenic temperature has attracted increasing attention[1-3]. Resin transfer molding (RTM) could prepare the composites with complex structures, and has been widely applied in the manufacture of many composite structures [4]. The development of epoxy resin matrix composites for RTM process will greatly promote the progress of cryogenic engineering.

Owing to their high mechanical properties, good thermal and corrosion resistance, and low curing shrinkage, epoxy resins have been widely used as matrix materials for structural composites[5-10]. However, the main drawback of epoxy resins is their inherent brittleness, leading to poor resistance to crack [11,12]. Therefore, epoxy matrix composites usually have low toughness, and are prone to impact damage and delamination, which limits their applications under cryogenic temperature [13-16].

Many approaches have been reported on the toughening of epoxy matrices. Most of them are based on the addition of a secondary phase such as liquid rubbers, thermoplastic, particulates or nanoparticles. However, the low viscosity was a prerequisite for epoxy resins to be applied in resin transfer molding (RTM). The viscosity of epoxy resin systems would be significantly increased as the rubber, thermoplastic, or particulate tougheners were added. The addition of even a small amount of nanoparticles could dramatically increase the viscosity of the resin systems. Moreover, during liquid resin infusion these toughening additives would be filtered by the reinforcing fabrics, and could not arrive at the effective toughening regions throughout the perform[17]. Besides, the thermal stress between epoxy phase and the secondary phase was disadvantage for the application under cryogenic temperature.

In the paper, the M40-level braiding fabric/R608 epoxy composites with excellent cryogenic mechanical properties and RTM processability were developed. The RTM processability was evaluated by rheological analysis. The thermal properties of the M40-level braiding fabric/R608 epoxy

composites were investigated by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMA). The effects of cryogenic temperature and (-196°C—80°C) cryogenic-cycles (as shown in Figure 1) on the mechanical properties of the M40-level braiding fabric/R608 epoxy composites were studied systemically.

Figure 1: Cryogenic-cycle curve for one cycle

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

2.1 RTM processability of R608 resin

Rheological measurement was performed to investigate the RTM processability of R608 resin. Viscosity versus temperature curve and Viscosity versus time curve under 45°C of R608 resin were tested. As shown in Figure 2, the RTM processing temperature window was wide.

Figure 2: Viscosity versus temperature curve of R608.

Figure 3: Viscosity versus time curve of R608 under 45°C.

The viscosity-time curves at 45°C in Figure 3 showed that R608 resin had a very wide RTM processing time window of more than 9 hours, which was enough for the manufacture of most composite parts, even the big composite structures.

2.2 Mechanical properties of R608 resin

The tensile properties, flexural properties, and impact properties were investigated under 80°C, RT and -196°C, respectively. As shown in Table 1, the breaking elongation of R608 resin at RT was as high as 6.1%, and the breaking elongation of R608 resin at -196°C was as high as 2.3%. Under -196°C, the small moving units of the polymer have been frozen, leading to the increase of the brittleness. Therefore, the breaking elongation of the R608 resin under -196°C decreased remarkably compared with that under RT. The impact strength of R608 resin under -196°C was as high as 24.1 kJ/m². While for many epoxy resin systems under -196°C, their breaking elongation was commonly lower than 2%, and their impact strength was generally lower than 20 kJ/m². Therefore, R608 resin has a relatively high ductility and impact strength at cryogenic temperature.

Test Temperature	80°C	RT	-196°C
Tensile Strength/MPa	50.3	86.8	65.7
Tensile Modulus/GPa	2.54	3.00	4.02
Breaking Elongation /%	5.1	6.1	2.3
Flexural Strength/MPa	98.6	134	221
Flexural Modulus/GPa	2.56	3.10	7.00
Impact Strength/kJ·m-2	33.8	27.5	24.1

Table 1 Mechanical properties of R608 resin under different temperature.

2.2 Thermal properties of composites

The DMA curve of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was measured in a nitrogen atmosphere to characterize the thermal properties. From Figure 4, the T_g of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was 117°C, which could meet the usual requirement of thermal properties for

cryogenic composites. Combined with the result of mechanical properties under 80°C, R608 resin could meet the thermal requirement of 80°C.

Figure 4: DMA curve of the M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites.

2.3 Effects of cryogenic temperature on mechanical properties of composites

To find the effects of temperature on mechanical properties of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites, the tensile properties, flexural properties, compression properties, interlaminar shear properties and impact properties was tested under 80°C, RT and -196°C, respectively.

Figure 5: Tensile strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature.

From Figure 5, it is obvious that the tensile strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature keep stable. While as shown in Figure 6, as the temperature dropped from 80°C to -196°C, the flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites improved about 44%. Moreover, as the temperature reduced from 80°C to -196°C, the flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites greatly improved about 75% as given in Figure 7.

Figure 6: Flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature.

Figure 7: Compression strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature.

The improvement of interlaminar shear strength and impact strength under cryogenic temperature has also been found in [Figure 8](#) and [Figure 9](#). As the temperature fell from 80°C to -196°C, the interlaminar shear strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites increased about 23%. And as the temperature dropped from 80°C to -196°C, impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites improved about 39%.

Figure 8: Interlaminar shear strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature.

Figure 9: Impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites under different temperature.

Flexural strength, compression strength, interlaminar shear strength and impact strength of composites can be greatly influenced by resin matrix. The effects of cryogenic temperature on mechanical properties of composites were mainly through resin matrix. In other word, the effects of cryogenic temperature are large for the mechanical properties which are greatly influenced by resin matrix. Therefore, Flexural strength, compression strength, interlaminar shear strength and impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites could be greatly influenced by cryogenic temperature.

2.3 Effects of cryogenic-cycle on mechanical properties of composites

To investigate the effects of cryogenic-cycle on the mechanical properties M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites, 300 cryogenic-cycles have been performed between 80 °C and -196 °C according to the cryogenic-cycle curve in Figure 1. Tensile strength, Flexural strength, Compression strength, Interlaminar shear strength, and Impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites before cryogenic-cycle, after 100 cryogenic-cycles, and after 300 cryogenic cycles have been tested and the results were summarized in Figure 11-14.

Figure 10: Tensile strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

As shown in Figure 10, after 100 cryogenic-cycles, the tensile strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was improved; and after 300 cryogenic-cycles, the tensile strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites decreased slightly, but still higher than that before cryogenic-cycles.

Figure 11: Flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

From Figure 11, it is obvious that after 100 cryogenic-cycles, the flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites declined; and after 300 cryogenic-cycles, the flexural strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites increased slightly.

Figure 12: Compression strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

As presented in Figure 12, after 100 cryogenic-cycles, the compression strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was improved; and after 300 cryogenic-cycles, the compression strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites kept stable. Besides, after 100 and 300

cryogenic-cycles, interlaminar shear strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites has no obvious change as given in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Interlaminar shear strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

Figure 14: Impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

After 100 cryogenic-cycles, the impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was increased slightly; and after 300 cryogenic-cycles, the impact strength of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites decline slightly.

From the result above, it seems that after 100 cryogenic-cycles, the mechanical properties of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites generally changed slight ; and after 300 cryogenic-cycles, the mechanical properties of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites became stable. The similar results also be found in fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites. Both G_{IC} and G_{IIC} were improved slight after 100 cryogenic-cycles, while after 300 cryogenic-cycles, they all decreased slight, but still higher than that before cryogenic-cycles.

Figure 15: G_{IC} of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

Figure 16: G_{IIC} of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after different numbers of the cryogenic-cycles.

2.4 Fracture features

Figure 17: SEM images of fracture features for M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites after (a) 0, (b) 100, and (c) 300 cryogenic-cycles .

The fracture feature of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites before cryogenic-cycles and after 100 and 300 cryogenic-cycles were measured by SEM. As shown in Figure 17, the micro-morphologies have not changed obviously after 100 and 300 cryogenic-cycles, indicating a good resistibility for the cryogenic-cycles.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The epoxy resin matrix composites with excellent cryogenic mechanical properties and RTM processability were developed. The RTM processing time window of R608 resin was more than 9 h. The breaking elongation of R608 was as high as 6.1% at RT and as high as 2.3% at -196°C, respectively. The T_g of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites was 117°C. The cryogenic temperature had no obvious effect on tensile strength of the M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites. While as the temperature dropped from 80°C to -196°C, the flexural strength, compression strength, interlaminar shear strength and impact strength were improved remarkably. After 300 cryogenic-cycles, the mechanical strength and fracture toughness of M40-level braiding fabric/R608 composites have no obvious decline, indicating that the composites could effectively resist the (-196°C—80°C) cryogenic-cycles.

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